
Deliverable D-JRP12-1.1

Report on an initial assessment of long-read sequencing for metagenome (community and AMR) analysis (defined community, spiked and real simple and complex matrices) and comparison to current short-read standard

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED

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1. Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the greatest global public health concerns in modern times. Current AMR and pathogen diagnostics are reliant on time-consuming culture-based approaches. However, employing these classical microbiological (i.e. culture-based) techniques for the identification of pathogens and AMR from complex samples can be onerous, time consuming and fail to provide a comprehensive analysis of the microbiome¹, i.e. the entire microbial community present and their resistome i.e. AMR genes (ARG) present within the bacterial community. The development of new tools for real-time detection of resistant pathogens is a priority topic of the One Health EJP. Metagenomic sequencing, analysis of the microbiome, using short-read data can detect the composition of microbial communities for the assessment of potential pathogens and AMR or virulence genes, which could become an invaluable diagnostic tool. However, short-read technologies are dependent on large laboratory instruments with significant analysis time, thereby impeding real-time analysis. Moreover, the short reads cannot reliably detect the presence of a complete gene of interest in a species, nor associate individual genes in a community to specific organisms, which is a limitation for detecting AMR in pathogens.

The FARMED project aimed to address these issues by using the long-read sequencing technology, as offered by Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT). The ONT MinION flow cell is a portable real-time device (100 grams), generating, in real-time, up to 30 Gb of DNA sequencing. The longer lengths (>1000 bp) of DNA sequence data enable the user to find complete ARGs, and theoretically also associations with bacteria and ARGs, in real-time, without the need for traditional whole genome sequencing of isolates (WGS). As such, by using long-read metagenomic sequencing, the local genetic context of ARGs can be derived. This technology will enable the identification of a plethora of bacterial species within the bacterial community ('microbiome'), the ARGs present in the community ('resistome') and potentially the linkage of species to a range of ARGs. In addition, the ONT technology has the potential to offer real-time and on-site (because of its portability) detection of AMR/virulence genes of pathogens and commensal bacteria in a plethora of sample matrices, thus aiding clinicians and veterinarians in applying effective treatments and management practices. A fast and effective on-site monitoring of these sample matrices will contribute to the prevention and early detection of pathogens infecting humans and/or animals.

However, the challenges of developing and implementing a robust workflow for on-site work with limited field facilities and minimal costs still remain (cfr. deliverable WP3 D-JRP12-3.1; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557> and deliverable WP3 D-JRP12-3.5; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433281>). We addressed this issue in FARMED by first demonstrating preliminary usage of metagenomic long-read sequencing for testing of different sample matrices, to characterise the microbiome and resistome (and potential for linkage), that could be adapted for on-site purposes in future work (cfr. deliverable WP3 D-JRP12-3.5; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433281>). We compared the metagenomic outputs from the ONT MinION to the current gold standard short-read (Illumina) technology and to PacBio long-read sequencing technology. We assessed ONT's ability for diagnostic use

¹ Marchesi, J.R., Ravel, J. The vocabulary of microbiome research: a proposal. *Microbiome* 3, 31 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-015-0094-5>

on a range of sample matrices. These matrices were derived from different origins, covering the One Health spectrum, i.e. human and animal samples, but also food/feed and environmental samples, as these may be a source of AMR and/or pathogens. DNA has been prepared using standard laboratory protocols. This needed to provide information on whether it is feasible to use ONT MinION sequencing to gain insight about pathogen and AMR detection within ‘simple’ and ‘complex’ matrices, and requirements for further adjustments.

This deliverable D-JRP12-1.1 will summarise the investigation of the feasibility of using ONT sequencing to characterise the bacterial species and ARGs, within a matrix (performed within WP1 of FARMED). The initial investigation into the use of long-read metagenomic sequencing was tested using two different ‘defined’ microbial communities, and subsequently, on ‘real’ sample matrices (Table 1). The matrices were divided into simple (i.e. a limited number of bacteria expected, e.g., water) and complex (i.e. either multiple bacteria present, or difficult DNA extraction, such as faeces (human and animal), milk, environmental (e.g., wastewater, boot swabs) and food/feed samples). We used current off-the-shelf laboratory methods for DNA extraction (Table 2), library preparation and barcoding (Table 3). Data analysis was done using the k-mer alignment tool (KMA)² (see also deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>). Some of the long-read sequencing data was compared to the current standard that uses Illumina short-read sequencing or PacBio sequencing. Based on the obtained results, the feasibility of using ONT sequencing for bacterial species and AMR identification in different sample matrices (from a One Health perspective) in a diagnostic setting (i.e. not for the characterisation of the whole community as in microbiome studies) was evaluated and some recommendations from the FARMED consortium have been formulated.

Table 1. Overview of sample matrices analysed in this study

Defined microbial community	Simple matrix	Complex matrix
Mix of 6 bacterial species spiked in pond water (DMC-W)	Environmental: River water	Animal: faeces from pig, broiler, veal, cattle
Mix of 6 bacterial species spiked in buffalo faeces (DMC-F)	Environmental: Sprouts spent irrigation water	Human: faeces
Zymo gut microbial standard in PBS (GMS PURE)		Food/feed: supplements from microbial fermentation, Tahini/insect powder, bovine milk
Zymo gut microbial standard (GMS) spiked in various matrices (simple & complex): animal (chicken/pig/buffalo) faeces, river water, sprouts spent irrigation water, human faeces, bootsocks		Environmental: Bootsocks (= elastic cotton tubes pulled over the boots and termed 'socks' worn underneath the shoes plastic covering collect faecal droppings in poultry houses, containing faeces/dust)

² Clausen, P.T.L.C., Aarestrup, F.M. & Lund, O. Rapid and precise alignment of raw reads against redundant databases with KMA. BMC Bioinformatics 19, 307 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-018-2336-6>

Table 2. Overview of commercial DNA extraction kits used in this study

Institute	DNA extraction ID	Kit	Manufacturer
In-1	GenFind-1	GenFind V3 ¹	Beckman Coulter
In-2	Zymo	Quick-DNA HMW Magbead	Zymo Research
In-3	Zymo-2	Quick-DNA HMW Magbead ²	Zymo Research
	Maxwell	Maxwell16 automatic bead-based system	Promega
	Omega	E.Z.N.A.® Stool DNA Kit	Omega Bio-tek
In-4	Nuclisens	Nuclisens Easymag	BioMérieux
	Genfind-3	GenFind V3 ³	Beckman Coulter
	Genfind-4	GenFind V3 ⁴	Beckman Coulter
In-5	Zymo-5	Quick-DNA HMW Magbead ⁵	Zymo Research
In-6	Zymo-2	Quick-DNA HMW Magbead ²	Zymo Research
	Macherey	Nucleospin	Macherey-Nagel
In-7	Zymo-6	Quick-DNA HMW Magbead ⁶	Zymo Research
In-8	PureLink	PureLink Microbiome DNA Purification Kit	Thermofisher
	GenFind-3	GenFind V3 ³	Beckman Coulter
In-9	Zymo-7	Quick-DNA HMW MagBead ⁷	Zymo Research

Deviation from the manufacturer's protocol can be found here:

¹: Lysis stage: Up to 200mg of faecal sample resuspended in 200ul of PBS, RNase step skipped, following the 2h incubation at 65C the sample is centrifuged at 5000xg for 5min to collect the supernatant for the binding stage (pellet discarded); Bind stage: after adding Bind (BBB) solution, sample placed onto Hula Mixer (slow speed) for 30min at room temperature; Wash stage: pellet dried for 1-2min before eluting it in nuclease-free water.

²: MetaPolyzyme 1h at 37°C; Proteinase K 30 min; MagBinding Beads on a rotor for 20 min; drying of the beads less than 10 min at 55°C to avoid over drying; elution in a thermo shaker at 55°C for 10 min.

³: Lysozyme prelysis

⁴: Bead-beating prelysis

⁵: MetaPolyzyme for 1h at 37°C; Proteinase K for 30 min; Bead binding for 20 min on a Hula rotor; elution at 55°C for 10 min.

⁶: Proteinase K 30 min; Binding to 40 µl of beads, instead of 33 µl, for 20 min on a rotor; drying of the beads 10 min at 55°C; elution in 35 µl of elution buffer, instead of 50 µl, at 55°C during 10 min in a shaker.

⁷: MetaPolyzyme 2h at 37°C; Proteinase K 30 min; Binding to beads 20 min on a rotor; drying of the beads 7 min at 55°C; elution at 55°C during 10 min in a shaker

2. Assessment of feasibility of ONT long-read metagenomics based on 'defined' microbial communities for species and ARG detection and identification

To assess the feasibility of long-read sequencing for metagenomics, we first used DNA isolated, using standard techniques, from a defined bacterial community containing isolates from various bacterial species (Gram negative and Gram positive, with available WGS data) to demonstrate long-read sequencing ability to resolve the community. Two defined bacterial communities were used, i.e. i) an in-house prepared mixture of six different microbial isolates, with different AMR profiles, in two different sample matrices ('DMC') and ii) a commercially available mock community consisting of 15 different species at different concentrations (Gut microbial standard, GMS), that was analysed 'pure', but also spiked in simple and complex matrices. MinION sequencing was used for all samples. The long-read sequencing output was compared to i) the known spiked species/AMR content, ii) the output of short read sequencing and iii) the output of PacBio long-read sequencing (selection of samples only).

Table 3. Overview of MinION* library preparation and barcoding kits used in this study

Institute	ONT settings ID ¹	Library preparation	Barcoding	Multiplexing level	Sequencing time (hrs)	Basecalling accuracy	Reads min quality filtering	Reads min length filtering (bp)
In-1	Lig-3plex-72-hac-10	Ligation	Native 114	2 to 3	66-72	High	10	500
	Rap-6plex-48-hac-9	Rapid ²	Rapid	5 to 6	48	High	8-9	none
In-2	Lig-3plex-48-hac-8	Ligation	Native 104 and 114	3	48	High	8	none
In-3	Lig-3plex-72-hac-7	Ligation	Native 114	3	72	High	7	none
In-4	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Ligation	Native 104	4	46-72	Super high	9	none
In-5	Lig-3plex-48-fas-7	Ligation	Native 104	3	48	Fast	7	none
	Lig-5plex-48-fas-7	Ligation	Native 104	5	48	Fast	7	none
In-6	Lig-1plex-72-sup-10	Ligation	No barcoding	1	72	Super high	10	500
	Lig-3plex-72-sup-10	Ligation	Native 104	3	72	Super high	10	500
In-7	Lig-2plex-21-hac-7	Ligation	Native 114	2	21.35	High	7	500
In-8	Lig-6plex-24-hac-9	Ligation	Native (104 and 114)	6	24	High	9	none
	PCR-6plex-24-hac-9	PCR barcoding	PCR barcoding	6	24	High	9	none
	Rap-6plex-6-hac-9	Rapid	Rapid	6	6	High	9	none
	Fie-1plex-6-hac-9	Field	No barcoding	1	6	High	9	none
In-9	Lig-2plex-72-fas-10	Ligation	Native 114	2	72	Fast	10	500

Ligation: Ligation sequencing genomic DNA (SQK-LSK109); Rapid: Rapid sequencing genomic DNA - barcoding (SQK-RBK004); Field: Rapid sequencing gDNA - Field Sequencing Kit (SQK-LRK001); PCR-barcoding: Ligation sequencing genomic DNA - PCR barcoding (SQK-LSK109 with EXP-PBC 096); Native 104: Native Barcoding Expansion 1-12 (EXP-NBD104); Native 114: Native Barcoding Expansion 13-24 (EXP-NBD114); *MinION: FLO-MIN 106D R.9.4.1; ¹: ONT settings identifiers are composed of the following information "*library_preparation-multiplex_level-sequencing_time-basecalling_accuracy-min_reads_quality*"; lig: ligation; rap: rapid; PCR: PCR barcoding; Fie: field; Nplex: multiplex of level *N*; fas: fast; hac: high accuracy; sup: super high accuracy. ²: with modifications: The AMPure XP bead incubation on the Hula mixer and sample eluted in 10 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5-8.0 with 50 mM NaCl incubation at room temperature were extended to 20min and 5 min, respectively.

2.1 DMC

A DMC of four Gram-negative isolates and two Gram-positive isolates with known complete genome sequences and different AMR profiles was used to assess robustness and reliability of DNA extraction methods for long-read sequencing. These six isolates were assembled into two differently composed communities, either with a fixed concentration (FF or WF) of 10^5 CFU/ml or with a range (FM or WM) from 10^3 to 10^7 CFU/ml (summarised in table 4). Two different sample matrices, buffalo faeces (complex matrix, F) and pond water (simple matrix, W) were spiked with this DMC. Blank water (WB) and blank faecal samples (FB) (no DMC added) were used as controls. The matrix samples were screened for *Salmonella*, and ESBL and/ or Carbapenemase producing *Enterobacteriaceae* as well as isolates harbouring the *mcr-1* to *mcr-9* genes and found them to be free and suitable for the DMC analysis. The commercial nucleic acid preservation solution (DNA/RNA Shield, Zymo Research) was selected and used to store the spiked mock community and their matrices.

Table 4. The concentration of bacteria used to spike complex and simple matrices

Bacteria	Fixed Concentration (FF/WF) DMC (CFU/ml)	Mixed Concentration (FM/WM) DMC (CFU/ml)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	10^5	10^3
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	10^5	10^3
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	10^5	10^5
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	10^5	10^5
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	10^5	10^7
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	10^5	10^7

DNA extractions were carried out using an already established/used protocol at each participating institute (Table 2). These involved mainly commercially available kits, based on different lysis principles, including bead beating, enzymatic lysis or a mixture of both. The concentration of DNA extracted by the various methods ranged from 1 to 60 ng/ μ l of DNA, with satisfactory 260/280 ratio (1.6-1.8). The range of DNA fragment sizes (3-50 kb) also varied between the methods. The project partners used the same long-read sequencing kits (ONT Ligation sequencing kit (SQK-LSK109) and native barcoding Expansion (EXP-NBD104 and EXP-NBD114)) in order to obtain comparable sequencing results between the consortium. DNA was sequenced with Illumina short-read (these varied between the consortium) and ONT-MinION (Flow Cell R9.4.1) long-read sequencing technologies, aiming to achieve 5 Gb per sample.

The FARMED KMA parameters (cfr. Deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>) were used to compare the Illumina and MinION output of DMC samples from the institutes (Table 5). As expected, generally, the Illumina sequencing identified the DMC bacterial species at a greater number of reads compared to MinION. However, there were several examples where species were only detected albeit at low level in the MinION data. For example, *S. enterica* was not detected in institute 3 and 6 Illumina data from fixed faecal (FF) samples, where a high read count was found in the MinION data. Illumina data from institute 6 was unable to detect *A. baumannii*, *E. coli*, *S. enterica* and *V. cholerae*, which were detected in MinION data from the same FF sample. There was little difference between the Illumina and MinION data for the water samples (WF, WM), although

the number of read counts was higher in Illumina data. Interestingly, the MinION was able to detect 4 of the 6 spiked bacteria in the blank water (WB) samples. Similarly, in the blank faecal sample (FB), 4 out of the 6 spiked bacteria were detected with MinION. Surprisingly, given that faeces typically contain *E. coli*, this was only detected in the MinION data of 2 out of 5 mixed faecal (FM) samples and in none of the Illumina FM data, although *E. coli* was detected in most of the fixed faecal (FF) samples by both Illumina and MinION data. From these samples, the limit of detection for Illumina data appeared to be lower than for MinION data, which was able to detect the one of the lowest spiked species (*E. coli*).

Table 5. Variation of the number of ONT and Illumina reads for each of the DMC bacterial species

Illumina output								MinION output									
Institute_1	Sample type	DNA Method	<i>A. baumannii</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>V. cholerae</i>	Institute_1	Sample type	DNA Method	<i>A. baumannii</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>V. cholerae</i>
In-1	FB	E	-	-	+++	-	-	-	In-1	FB	E	-	-	++	-	-	-
In-3	FB	E	-	-	-	-	-	-	In-3	FB	E	-	+++	+++	-	-	+++
In-4	FB	M	-	-	-	-	-	-	In-4	FB	M	-	++	++	-	-	-
In-5	FB	E	-	-	-	-	-	-	In-5	FB	E	-	+++	-	-	++	++
In-6	FB	E	-	-	-	-	-	-	In-6	FB	E	-	++	-	-	-	-
In-8	FB		-	+	-	-	+++	-									
In-1	FF	E	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	In-1	FF	E	-	-	+++	-	-	-
In-3	FF	E	+++	+++	+++	-	+++	+++	In-3	FF	E	-	+++	+++	+++	-	+++
In-4	FF	M	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	In-4	FF	M	++	+++	+++	++	++	++
In-5	FF	E	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	In-5	FF	E	++	+++	++	++	++	++
In-6	FF	E	-	+++	-	-	+++	-	In-6	FF	E	++	+++	++	++	-	+
In-8	FF	E	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++									
In-1	FM	E	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++	In-1	FM	E	-	-	-	-	-	-
In-3	FM	E	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++	In-3	FM	E	-	+++	+++	-	-	+++
In-4	FM	M	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++	In-4	FM	M	-	+++	++	++	-	+++
In-5	FM	E	-	+++	-	-	+++	+++	In-5	FM	E	-	+++	-	++	++	+++
In-6	FM	E	-	+++	-	-	+++	+++	In-6	FM	E	-	+++	-	-	++	+++
In-8	FM	E	-	+++	-	+++	+++	+++									
In-5	WB	E	-	-	-	-	-	-	In-5	WB	E	+	+++	-	-	+	+
In-6	WB	E	-	-	-	-	-	-	In-6	WB	E	-	++	-	-	+	+
In-5	WF	E	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	In-5	WF	E	++	+++	++	+	+++	++
In-6	WF	E	+++	+++	+++	-	+++	++	In-6	WF	E	++	+++	++	++	+++	++
In-5	WM	E	-	+++	-	+++	+++	+++	In-5	WM	E	-	+++	-	+	++	+++
In-6	WM	E	-	+++	-	-	+++	+++	In-6	WM	E	-	+++	-	++	++	+++

No of reads
0 - 1-10 + 11-100 ++ >100 +++

FB = faecal matrix, not spiked (blank); FF = faecal matrix spiked with fixed concentration DMC; FM = faecal matrix spiked with mixed concentration DMC; WB = water matrix, not spiked (blank); WF = water matrix spiked with fixed concentration DMC; WM = water matrix spiked with mixed concentration DMC; E = enzymatic extraction method; M = bead-beating extraction method

This difference in limit of detection between Illumina and ONT sequencing was further investigated using the In-4 data. A 'read-titration analysis' on the FF and FM samples was performed. With ONT sequencing we generated 2.9Gb data in the FF sample and identified 6 of 6 spiked-in genus' and 1.7Gb data in the FM sample and identified 5 of 6 spiked-in genus'. By Illumina sequencing, the FF sample generated 11.2Gb data and identified 1 of 6 species and the FM-sample generated 9.8Gb data and identified 2 of 6 species. ONT sequence data was then titrated to a level corresponding to the same level of genus identification (i.e.

systematically downscaling of reads and then comparing the number of bases between sequencing technologies where the same amount of genus' were found, as evaluated based on ≥ 0.01 depth). Compared to Illumina, ONT sequencing was ca. 200 and 2000 times more efficient in genus identification on the FF and FM sample, respectively (Table 6). Despite the lower number of reads per total Mb ONT sequence data, the longer ONT reads contain more information allowing a more precise genus/species identification.

Table 6. Read titration analysis on FF and FM samples

Sample	Technology	Number of bases (Mb)	Depth	Number of spiked species identified
FF	Illumina	11,600	≥ 0.01	1/6
			< 0.01	0/6
	ONT	50	≥ 0.01	1/6
			< 0.01	5/6
FM	Illumina	9,800	≥ 0.01	2/6
			< 0.01	0/6
	ONT	5	≥ 0.01	2/6
			< 0.01	1/6

In-6 observed that when pooling 3 samples on a MinION flow cells, a lot of information was lost because more than half of the sequenced reads were not properly demultiplexed and remained "unclassified". Re-sequencing of the DMC samples with one sample per flow cell increased the number of reads produced per sample (although the 2 lowest abundant species were still not detected) and no data was lost as "unclassified" or "misclassified" (as no demultiplexing was required).

The difference between extraction methods could not be fully established due to data availability, however enzymatic methods (In-1, In-3, In-5, In-6) were the most common but showed variation between samples. Only one sample extracted using bead-beating (In-4) appeared to detect all spiked species in the fixed faeces (FF) samples sequenced using MinION, however it must be noted that In-5 which used an enzyme method also detected all spiked species. Using spiking experiments, further analysis is required to determine the detection limits, which may be influenced by the extraction method used.

Comparison of the microbial profile of faecal samples, using ordination analysis, the samples clustered differently depending on the reference database used. Illumina data appeared to cluster according to institute (likely due to different DNA extraction methods employed at each institute) when using the 16S SILVA database, whereas when the FARMED_db (complete genomes) was used, the samples clustered based on sample type rather than by institute or DNA method (Figure 1). However, for MinION data the clustering was less clear where the samples for two institutes (In-1, In-3, using different DNA extraction kits) clustered together using the SILVA database, whereas using the FARMED_db, generally separated according to either blank (FB) or mixed concentration (FM) sample type, except for institute 1, which clustered together. For institutes 4, 5 and 6, the blank and fixed concentration samples appear to cluster together whereas their mixed concentration samples clustered with the fixed concentration from sample from institute 3.

Figure 1. Ordination analysis plots based on Illumina (short reads) and ONT (long-reads) sequence data demonstrate the distribution bacteria genera in of analysed faeces samples.

Comparison of the AMR class profile of faecal samples showed different clustering patterns when using either MinION or Illumina data (Figure 2). For all 5 institutes, the Illumina data for the blank (FB) and fixed concentration (FF) samples overlapped and the mixed concentration (FM) samples clustered separately; whereas for the MinION data, the mixed (FM) and blank (FB) displayed clustering but the fixed (FF) samples did not.

Figure 2. Ordination analysis plots based on Illumina (short reads) and ONT (long-reads) sequence data demonstrate the distribution of AMR class in faeces samples.

In summary, generally MinION sequencing was able to identify the spiked bacteria depending on the DNA extraction method as well as the sequencing method employed. The difference observed in the bacterial composition of samples was likely due to the depth of sequencing undertaken. It is encouraging that although there was variation in the sequencing, most were able to identify the spiked bacterial species in the DMC samples. Three DNA extraction methods were selected for further use to analyse samples (see section 2 GMS).

Sequencing Library Preparation

The aim of FARMED was to use long-read metagenomics on-site, which ideally would be short in time and consumables needed, therefore we assessed the different MinION options and whether similar sequencing data could be achieved. Two library preparation sequencing kits are offered by ONT: (1) the ligation library kit, which requires 1000 ng of DNA and takes approximately 4-5 hours (includes flow cell loading time) and (2) the rapid library kit, which only requires an input of 400 ng of DNA per sample and takes 1.5-2 hours (includes flow cell loading time). The ligation kit offers the option to select the fragment length size via the use of buffers, which intern yields in higher N50 read lengths. A further option exists for the sequencing run which differ in the accuracy of basecalling method: (1) high accuracy (HAC) with an accuracy of 97.8% and (2) 'fast' with an accuracy slightly less at 96.8%. Both library preparation kits and basecalling can be time-consuming stages thereby impacting timely delivery of results. Using the same DNA extraction method (GenFind V3 kit, Beckman Coulter) on the same three DMC faecal samples (FB, FF, FM), we compared the two options for library preparation and basecalling approaches. For multiplexing, barcodes provided in the Rapid barcoding kit were used whereas Native barcoding expansion kit (EXP-NBD104) were used with the Ligation sequencing kit. Finally, the long fragment buffer (LBF) was used in library preparations using the Ligation sequencing kit. Sequencing was then performed on separate FLO-MIN106D R9.4.1 flow cells (Flow cell 1 – library prep done using Rapid barcoding kit; Flow cell 2 – library prep done using Ligation sequencing kit). Short-read sequencing required only 1 ng of DNA; sequencing was performed on NextSeq 500/550 generating 2x150bp paired-end reads.

The sequencing output (Figure 3) for rapid library preparation whether fast or HAC basecalling was used, was 0.313 - 0.394 Gb, whereas the output from the Ligation preparation was significantly greater, between 3.7 - 5.8Gb. There were 10 - 20 times more bases sequenced by the ligation library preparation kit (~2,839,263,364bp) compared to rapid library (~211,138,482bp), which may be due to the starting concentration of DNA used in ligation library preparation kit. Short-read sequencing provides deep genome coverage while long-read sequencing, although producing long fragments (> 1000 bp), has lower depth, making biological comparisons across sequencing platforms difficult.

Comparison of the bacterial profiles (Figure 4) showed that samples tended to separate according to library preparation method used, where samples sequenced using Illumina appeared to be located between ligation and rapid prepared samples. The basecalling mode did not appear to have a large influence on the results, where the microbial profiles appear similar whether using HAC and Fast mode. The ligation library kit and the high accuracy (HAC) basecalling identified more species compared to the rapid library kit and the fast basecalling (average 182 vs 29 species). With respect to AMR (Figure 4), samples sequenced using Illumina separated from MinION sequenced samples and there was less distinction between the

MinION library preparation and basecalling approached used.

Figure 3. Number of reads and sequence length per sample and per library preparation type

Figure 4. Ordination analysis plots based on different library preparation and basecalling technology generated sequence data demonstrate the distribution of bacteria genera (left) AMR class (right) in faeces samples. Each symbol is label with sample type: FB, blank (unspiked); FF, fixed concentration; FM, mixed concentration.

Illumina was able to identify the majority of spiked bacteria (Table 7). However, although more genera and species were identified using the ligation library preparation, the rapid library preparation sequencing showed comparable results to Illumina, detecting most of the DMC spiked species, although the level of reads for each spiked bacteria appeared to be lower. The basecalling approach had little effect on the identification of the spiked bacteria, which is the preferable option for on-site sequencing. The results suggested that using the quicker less labour-intensive library preparation could be suitable for the identification of pathogens rather than the exploration of all microbiomes species, but a minimum depth of MinION sequencing is required.

Table 7. Summary of DMC species identified in DMC samples sequenced using different library preparations and basecalling

Sample type	WGS type	Library prep	base-calling	<i>Acinetobacter</i>	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Escherichia</i>	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Staphylococcus</i>	<i>Vibrio</i>	<i>A. baumannii</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>V. cholerae</i>
FB	Illumina	Illumina	Illumina	++	++	+++	++	++	-	-	+	+++	++	-	-
FB	MinION	Ligation	Fast	++	+++	+++	-	+++	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-
FB	MinION	Ligation	HAC	++	+++	++	-	+++	-	-	-	++	-	-	-
FB	MinION	Rapid	Fast	-	+	+++	-	-	-	-	+	+++	-	-	-
FB	MinION	Rapid	HAC	-	++	+++	-	-	-	-	++	+++	-	-	-
FF	Illumina	Illumina	Illumina	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
FF	MinION	Ligation	Fast	+++	+++	+++	-	+++	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-
FF	MinION	Ligation	HAC	+++	+++	+++	-	+++	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-
FF	MinION	Rapid	Fast	++	++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+++	++	++	+
FF	MinION	Rapid	HAC	++	++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+++	++	++	++
FM	Illumina	Illumina	Illumina	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++	-	+++
FM	MinION	Ligation	Fast	++	+++	++	-	+++	-	-	-	++	-	-	-
FM	MinION	Ligation	HAC	+++	+++	++	-	+++	-	-	-	++	-	-	-
FM	MinION	Rapid	Fast	++	+++	+++	++	-	+++	-	+++	+++	++	-	+++
FM	MinION	Rapid	HAC	-	+++	+++	++	-	+++	-	+++	+++	++	-	+++

No of reads
 0 - 1-10 + 11-100 ++ >100 +++

PacBio Long Read Metagenomics

PacBio offers a non-portable instrument able to perform long-read sequencing. The DMC samples were also sequenced with PacBio long-read sequencing by one institute. The output was compared to ONT and short read sequencing, both for species identification and AMR detection (Table 8). When sequencing the blank faecal (BF) matrix, analysis of the data generated by ONT and Illumina technologies identified four or three of the members of the defined mock community, respectively. On the other hand, none of these bacterial species was identified in the more accurate circular consensus sequencing (CCS)³ data by PacBio although in the data based on subreads⁴, *E. coli* could be identified. Along similar lines, the addition of the defined mock community in a fixed concentration (FF) was identified in the ONT and Illumina data sets, as the additional bacterial species belonging to *Salmonella*, *Acinetobacter* and *Escherichia* in the case of Illumina could be identified. The spiking of the fixed defined mock community was not identified in either CSS or subread data sets of PacBio. Analysis of the data generated by addition of the mixed defined mock community (FM) yielded similar results. Although only four of the bacterial species could be identified by both ONT and Illumina sequencing, PacBio data only yielded identification of *E. coli* in the subreads data set. Specifically, both ONT and Illumina sequencing did not identify the lowest (10⁻³) spiked species, *A. baumannii* and *E. coli* species.

³ The consensus sequence resulting from alignment between subreads taken from a single zero-mode waveguide (part of a SMRT Cell). Generating a CCS read does not include or require alignment against a reference sequence but does require at least two full-pass subreads from the insert. CCS reads are highly accurate (>99% accuracy, Q>20).

⁴ Each polymerase read is partitioned to form one or more subreads, which contain sequence from a single pass of a polymerase on a single strand of an insert within a SMRTbell template and no adapter sequences. The subreads contain the full set of quality values and kinetic measurements.

Table 8. Comparison ONT-PacBio-Illumina sequencing

	ONT	Illumina	PacBio
Sequencing Methodology	SQK-LSK109	NextSeq 500, Hi-Output	Sequel II
Multiplex ?	triplex	triplex	triplex
Identification of defined mock community species?	Faecal matrix only (BF)	Identification of <i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>V. cholerae</i> and <i>B. subtilis</i>	CSS : Did not identify any of the defined mock community's species Subreads : identified <i>E. coli</i>
	Faecal matrix + fixed DMC (FF)	Identification of all 6 bacterial species	Both CSS and subreads : Did not identify any of the defined mock community's species
	Faecal matrix + mixed DMC (FM)	Identification of <i>S. enterica</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>V. cholerae</i> , and <i>B. subtilis</i> Did not identify : <i>A. baumannii</i> and <i>E. coli</i>	Identification of <i>S. enterica</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>V. cholerae</i> , and <i>B. subtilis</i> Did not identify : <i>A. baumannii</i> and <i>E. coli</i> CSS : Did not identify any of the defined mock community's species Subreads : identified <i>E. coli</i>
AMR detection	Faecal matrix (BF)	Detection of 15 ARGs	Detection of 50 ARGs
	Faecal matrix + fixed DMC (FF)	Detection of 15 ARGs	Detection of 80 ARGs
	Faecal matrix + mixed DMC (FM)	Detection of 24 ARGs	Detection of 78 ARGs
			Detection of 4 ARGs using both CSS and subreads
			Identification of 4 ARGs using CSS and 3 additional ARGs when using subreads
			Detection of 4 ARGs when using CSS and 5 further ARGs when using subreads.

Analyses with KMA (v.1.3.28) using the FARMED_db and the ResFinder database from 2022

For the AMR analysis, the total number of identified ARGs was highest across all three sample types in the Illumina data sets, while the fewest number of ARGs were identified in the PacBio data. For all three datasets of PacBio data, the more accurate CSS data yielded fewer ARGs than competing technologies. Although analysis using the subread data identified additional ARGs than when using CSS, the total number of ARGs was still below the results by ONT.

Overall, both the ONT and Illumina sequencing technologies fared better at both identifying the spiking of the defined mock community (both in fixed and mixed concentrations) than the PacBio technology. Particularly, at the fixed concentration, all six constituent members of the mock community could be correctly identified. When identifying ARGs, again, both the ONT and Illumina data yielded higher numbers in total ARGs, although the number of variants of one gene was particularly high in the Illumina data, e.g. when more than 25 different *tet* genes were identified in the mixed DMC sample. Furthermore, the high requirement of input DNA concentrations as well a lengthy library preparation time of two days underlined that PacBio does not serve as a suitable long-read alternative, since the quality of its data output did not compensate for the additional workload needed or the higher costs in respect of metagenomic demands. Based on these results, in addition to PacBio sequencing not being open to all (requires high upfront investments), it was not further included in the comparisons.

2.2 GMS

Based on DMC analysis, the consortium selected three commercially available DNA extraction kits for further investigation (Table 9), using real-life ‘simple’ and ‘complex’ matrices of choice for the respective institutes. For evaluation, a commercially available mock community (ZymoBIOMICS Gut Microbiome Standard, GMS, CAT no D6331, Zymo Research), was utilised to identify and achieve a consistent output between different users, and allowed comparison of methods between partners in the consortium. This GMS was also analysed in PBS (i.e. ‘pure’, without spiking into a matrix).

The range of DNA extracted by each institute was comparable between the DNA extraction kits used. The minimum amount of DNA required for Nanopore sequencing library preparation is either 400 ng (rapid, in 7.5 µl i.e. 53.3 ng/µl) or 1000 ng (ligation, in 48 µl i.e. 20.8 ng/µl), so for many of the extraction kits, the quantities were sufficient to process with long-read sequencing (Table 9). The sequencing data was analysed using KMA for taxonomic classification with FARMED_db or home-made curated database and ARG detection with ResFinder database (cfr. Deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>).

Table 9. DNA concentration obtained with the 3 different kits on the 3 different sample inputs

Sample	DNA concentration (ng/µl)		
	Gen Find V3	Pure Link Genomic DNA mini kit	Quick DNA HMW magbead kit
GMS (‘pure’)	31 – 39	17.6	24 – 33
Simple matrix (water)	N/D	N/D	52 – 55.2
Complex matrix (faeces)	102 – 139	50.2	102 – 113

N/D: Not Determined.

Overall, for institutes using the FARMED_db database, species were better detected with Nanopore singleplex than with Nanopore triplex or Illumina, attesting the feasibility of using this technology for metagenomics analysis. Nevertheless, the accuracy and sensitivity of the sequencing were greatly influenced by experimental settings, such as the DNA extraction method, the library preparation kit, the level of multiplexing or the basecalling accuracy (Table 10, 11 and 12). The different combination of experimental settings can be sorted from "ideal settings" (i.e. singleplex, 72h, ligation kit and Quick-DNA HMW MagBeat kit) to "cost-time efficient settings" (i.e. 6plex, 24h, rapid kit and GenFind V3 kit). It appeared that, the more the experimental settings go from ideal to cost-time efficient, the more the detection accuracy and sensitivity decreased, both being not anymore comparable to Illumina sequencing. It appears that the GenFind V3, Pure Link and Quick DNA HMW kits produced different results depending on the samples examined (Table 10, 12). Quick DNA HMW kit with Metapolyzyme seemed to perform usually better. Adding the bead-beating step to the GenFind V3 protocol increased the number of GMS species detected. Moreover, the results were also influenced by the choice of the database but this was more extensively discussed in Deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>).

Table 10. KMA results for species detection in the PURE GMS sample

Species in GMS	Relat. abund.	Nbr of cells	GC %	Gram	Institutes and experimental settings ¹										
					In-1	In-2 ²	In-3	In-4	In-4	In-5	In-6	In-6	In-6	In-7 ³	In-9
					GenFind-1	Zymo	Zymo-2	GenFind-3	GenFind-4	Zymo-5	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	Yymo-6	Zymo-7
					Rap-6plex-48-hac-9	Lig-3plex-48-hac-8	Lig-3plex-72-hac-7	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Lig-5plex-48-fas-7	Lig-1plex-72-sup-10	Lig-3plex-72-sup-10	Illumina	Lig-2plex-21-hac-7	Lig-2plex-72-fas-10
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	50.0	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i> ⁴	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	57.8	+	-	+	+	+/-	+/-	-	+/-	+/-	+/-	+	+/-
<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	39.0	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	48.7	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	43.3	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	44.4	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	59.2	+	+/-	+	+	+	+/-	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	27.0	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	52.3	+	+/-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Clostridioides/dium difficile</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	28.8	+	+	+/-	+	-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	55.5	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	0.10%	2 × 10 ⁵	31.0	+	-	+/-	+	-	+/-	-	+	+/-	+/-	-	+/-
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01%	2 × 10 ⁴	52.2	-	-	+	+/-	-	+/-	-	+/-	-	-	-	+/-
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001%	2 × 10 ³	37.5	+	-	+/-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0.0001%	2 × 10 ²	28.3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Relat. abund.: relative abundance as communicated by the manufacturer; Nbr of cells: Number of cells; GC %: GC content in percent.

¹: according to DNA extraction ID in table 2 and ONT settings ID in table 3; ²: manually curated -in-house database used for KMA analysis, while all other analyses were done with the FARMED_db; ³: overall low yield of ONT reads obtained; ⁴: The detection of *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* by some institutes suffered from database issues as discussed in deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>.

+: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace.

Table 11. KMA results for species detection in the spiked simple matrix

Species in GMS	Relative abundance	Number of cells	GC content (%)	Gram	Institutes, experimental settings and simple matrices ¹	
					In-7 ²	In-9
					Zymo-6	Zymo-7
					Lig-2plex-21-hac-7	Lig-2plex-72-fas-10
					Sprout irrigation water	River water
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	50.0	-	+/-	+
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	57.8	+	+/-	+/-
<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	39.0	-	+/-	+
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	48.7	+/-	+/-	+
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	43.3	-	+/-	+
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	44.4	-	+/-	+
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	59.2	+	+/-	+
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	27.0	-	+/-	+
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	52.3	+	+/-	+
<i>Clostridioides/dium difficile</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	28.8	+	-	+
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	55.5	-	-	+
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	0.10%	2 × 10 ⁵	31.0	+	-	+/-
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01%	2 × 10 ⁴	52.2	-	-	+/-
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001%	2 × 10 ³	37.5	+	-	-
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0.0001%	2 × 10 ²	28.3	+	-	-

¹: according to DNA extraction ID in table 2 and ONT settings ID in table 3; ²: overall low yield of ONT reads obtained

+: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace.

Table 12. KMA results for species detection in the spiked complex matrix

Species in GMS					Institutes, experimental settings and matrix ¹												
					In-1	In-2 ²	In-2 ²	In-3	In-4	In-4	In-4	In-4	In-5	In-6	In-6	In-6	
					GenFind-1	Zymo	Zymo	Zymo-2	GenFind-3	GenFind-3	GenFind-4	GenFind-4	Zymo-5	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	
					Rap-6plex-48-hac-9	Lig-3plex-48-hac-8	Illumina Kapa PCR free	Lig-3plex-72-hac-7	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Lig-4plex-72-sup-9	Lig-5plex-48-fas-7	Lig-1plex-72-sup-10	Lig-3plex-72-sup-10	Illumina	
Pig faeces	Pig faeces	Pig faeces	Chicken faeces	Human faeces A	Human faeces B	Human faeces A	Human faeces B	Buffalo faeces	Chicken faeces	Chicken faeces	Chicken faeces						
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	50.0	-	-	+	+	+	+/-	+	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	57.8	+	-	+	+	+/-	-	-	-	-	-	+/-	+/-	+/-	
<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	39.0	-	-	+	+	+	+/-	+	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	48.7	+/-	-	+	+	+	+/-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	43.3	-	-	+	+	+	+/-	+/-	-	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	44.4	-	+/-	+	+	+	+/-	+	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	59.2	+	-	+/-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	27.0	-	-	+/-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-	+/-	+	+	+/-	
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	52.3	+	-	+	+/-	+	+/-	+/-	-	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Clostridioides/dium difficile</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	28.8	+	-	+/-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-	+/-	+	+/-	+/-	
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	55.5	-	-	+/-	+/-	+	+	+/-	+	+/-	+/-	+	+/-	+	
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	0.10%	2 × 10 ⁵	31.0	+	-	+/-	+/-	+/-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01%	2 × 10 ⁴	52.2	-	-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001%	2 × 10 ³	37.5	+	-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0.0001%	2 × 10 ²	28.3	+	-	-	+/-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 12 (continued). KMA results for species detection in the spiked complex matrix

Relat. abund.: relative abundance as communicated by the manufacturer; Nbr of cells: Number of cells; GC %: GC content in percent.

¹: according to DNA extraction ID in table 2 and ONT settings ID in table 3; ²: manually curated -in-house database used for KMA analysis, while all other analyses were done

Species in GMS	Relat. abund.	Nbr of cells	GC %	Gram	Institutes, experimental settings and matrix ¹							
					In-8	In-8	In-8	In-8	In-8	In-8	In-8	In-8
					PureLink	PureLink	PureLink	PureLink	GenFind-3	GenFind-3	GenFind-3	GenFind-3
					Lig-6plex-24-hac-9	PCR-6plex-24-hac-9	Rap-6plex-6-hac-9	Fie-1plex-6-hac-9	Lig-6plex-24-hac-9	PCR-6plex-24-hac-9	Rap-6plex-6-hac-9	Fie-1plex-6-hac-9
					Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces	Cow Faeces
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	50.0	-	-	+/-	-	-	+/-	+/-	-	-
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	57.8	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	39.0	-	+/-	+	-	-	+/-	-	-	-
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	48.7	+/-	+/-	+/-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14%	3 × 10 ⁷	43.3	-	-	+/-	-	-	+/-	+/-	-	-
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	44.4	-	+/-	+/-	-	-	+/-	+/-	-	-
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	59.2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	27.0	-	-	+/-	-	-	-	+/-	-	-
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	6%	1 × 10 ⁷	52.3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Clostridioides/dium difficile</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	28.8	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	1.50%	3 × 10 ⁶	55.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	0.10%	2 × 10 ⁵	31.0	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01%	2 × 10 ⁴	52.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001%	2 × 10 ³	37.5	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0.0001%	2 × 10 ²	28.3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

with the FARMED_db; +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace

Table 13. KMA results for ARG detection in the PURE sample

ARG	Relative abundance	Host species	Institutes and experimental settings ¹						
			In-1	In-5	In-6	In-6	In-6	In-7 ²	In-9
			GenFind-1	Zymo-5	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	Zymo-6	Zymo-7
			Rap-6plex-48-hac-9	Lig-5plex-48-fas-7	Lig-1plex-72-sup-10	Lig-3plex-72-sup-10	Illumina	Lig-2plex-21-hac-7	Lig-2plex-72-fas-10
<i>tet(Q)</i>	20%	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i> and <i>Prevotella corporis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>mdf(A)</i>	14%	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>tet(W)</i>	14%	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+
<i>cepA</i>	14%	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>erm(B)</i>	1.50%	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	-	-	+	+	+	-	+
<i>aac(6')-laa</i>	0.01%	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	-	-	+	-	+/-	-	+/-
<i>lsa(A)</i>	0.001%	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

¹: according to DNA extraction ID in table 2 and ONT settings ID in table 3; ²: overall low yield of ONT reads obtained
 +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace.

Table 14. KMA results for ARG detection in the spiked simple sample

ARG	Relative abundance	Host species	Institutes, experimental settings and matrices ¹	
			In-7 ²	In-9
			Zymo-6	Zymo-7
			Lig-2plex-21-hac-7	Lig-2plex-72-fas-10
			Sprout irrigation water	River water
<i>tet(Q)</i>	20%	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i> and <i>Prevotella corporis</i>	-	+
<i>mdf(A)</i>	14%	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+
<i>tet(W)</i>	14%	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	-	+
<i>cepA</i>	14%	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	-	+
<i>erm(B)</i>	1.50%	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	-	+
<i>aac(6)-Iaa</i>	0.01%	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	-	-
<i>Isa(A)</i>	0.001%	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	-	-

¹: according to DNA extraction ID in table 2 and ONT settings ID in table 3; ²: overall low yield of ONT reads obtained
 +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace.

Table 15. KMA results for ARG detection in the spiked complex sample

ARG	Relative abundance	Host species ²	Institutes, experimental settings and matrices ¹						
			In-1	In-2	In-2	In-5	In-6	In-6	In-6
			GenFind-1	Zymo	Zymo	Zymo-5	Zymo-2	Zymo-2	Zymo-2
			Rap-6plex-48-hac-9	Lig-3plex-48-hac-8	Illumina Kapa PCR free	Lig-5plex-48-fas-7	Lig-1plex-72-sup-10	Lig-3plex-72-sup-10	Illumina
Pig faeces	Pig faeces	Pig faeces	Buffalo faeces	Chicken faeces	Chicken faeces	Chicken faeces			
<i>tet(Q)</i>	20%	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i> and <i>Prevotella corporis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>mdf(A)</i>	14%	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>tet(W)</i>	14%	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>cepA</i>	14%	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>erm(B)</i>	1.50%	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	+/-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>aac(6')-laa</i>	0.01%	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-
<i>lsa(A)</i>	0.001%	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	-	+/-	+	-	-	-	-

¹: according to DNA extraction ID in table 2 and ONT settings ID in table 3

²: species in which the ARG listed in the first column was detected in its full genome sequence using ResFinder and the reference genome sequence provided by the GMS manufacturer

+: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace

In the spiked simple and complex samples (Table 11, 12), some species were detected with a lower level of confidence than in the pure GMS sample, showing a possible effect of the matrix (see also section 3 and 4). Interestingly, in the spiked complex faecal samples, for some methods, *Bifidobacterium adolescentis* (at 6% relative abundance) and the species with relative abundance 0.1% or below could not be detected anymore (except when using a manually curated in-house database), independent of the sequencing method or the multiplexing level (Table 12), which indicates an effect of the matrix on the DNA extraction or sequencing. For the detection of *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, some institutes suffered from database issues (cfr. Deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>).

As to the AMR detection, maximum five out of the seven ARGs included in GMS could be correctly detected (i.e. with high mapping score) in the pure (Table 13) and spiked samples using ONT (Table 14, 15). One additional ARG (*aac(6')-Iaa*) was detected in the pure sample sequenced in Nanopore singleplex, compared to the sample run in triplicate (Table 13). The missing ARGs belonged to low abundant species which were also not detected during KMA taxonomic identification (Table 10, 12).

3. Feasibility of long-read metagenomics MinION from 'simple' sample matrices

Next, we used standard DNA isolation techniques (cfr. Table 2) on a selection of 'simple' sample matrices (i.e. a limited number of bacteria expected, such as water) (see Table 1), to evaluate the capability and practical feasibility of long-read sequencing to analyse the microbiome. 'Simple' sample matrices present challenges such a potentially low concentration of the bacterial community, which could affect ability of sequencing to resolve the community, to a level that is diagnostically beneficial to detect bacterial species and AMR determinant. Therefore, some sample pre-treatments (i.e. prior to DNA extraction) had to be put in place. A known bacterial community (i.e. GMS, cfr. point 2.2) was spiked in to determine limits of detection and evaluate the accuracy of bacterial species and detection of the presence of ARGs.

3.1 Simple matrix: river water

River water is classified as a simple matrix and, therefore, presents a low number of bacteria. This characteristic, coupled to the high amount of DNA required to perform long-read sequencing with MinION, makes a preliminary enrichment step essential. With river water we tested two possibilities: filtration and centrifugation. Filtration of large volumes of water (between 600 and 800 ml) rendered consistently between 1000 and 2000 ng of genomic DNA. However, the purity levels of the samples were very inconsistent, being rarely acceptable values. Sequencing of filtrated samples was attempted, leading to a rapid loss of the number of pores in the first hours of sequencing, obtaining a poor number of reads. On the other hand, centrifugation of different amounts of water and diverse centrifugation speeds and times was assessed. Centrifugation of a volume between 200 and 300 ml of river water at 6000 rpm for 2-3 hours was identified as the best combination to obtain similar concentrations as those obtained with the filtration method. Nevertheless, this new DNA extraction showed a better performance in the purity aspect, with suitable A260/280 and A260/230 ratios in most of the cases. Sequencing of a centrifugation sample spiked with GMS was performed, running for 72 hours without a problem. A good amount of data was obtained, with an acceptable read length and a good read quality. This was translated into detection of bacteria present in the

standard with relative abundances of 1.5% or greater with high confidence and species at relative abundances of 0.1% and 0.01% with lower confidence (cfr. Table 11). Also, the expected ARGs could be detected until relative abundance of 1.5% (cfr. Table 14). In addition, we were able to detect common species present in rivers, such as species from *Microcystis*, *Aurantimicrobium* or *Limnohabitans* genera. These results are very promising, pointing that not only MinION sequencing is feasible in water samples, but also that it is possible to detect low abundance species present in such simple matrices.

3.2 Simple matrix: irrigation water

Sprout spent irrigation water is one of the matrices mentioned in Reg. (EU) 209/2013, laying down microbiological criteria for testing the contamination of sprouts with Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*. Besides testing the possibility to apply a metagenomics approach based on Nanopore technology to this matrix, the aim was also to investigate the composition of the matrix in terms of species present in the water, as preliminary data have shown that STEC stability in these samples can be hindered by the natural microflora. The sample was initially tested for the presence of STEC applying ISO TS 13136, giving negative result. No positive samples were available in the lab. Tests were performed extracting DNA with Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit (Zymo Research) initially starting from 200 µl of sample, which did not produce appropriate yield (total 11 ng of DNA extracted). The use of a filtration step was excluded, due to the viscosity of the matrix. Several attempts were made for extracting DNA from sprouts spent irrigation water with the same extraction kit: starting from 200 µl of sample only allowed to obtain total 11 ng of DNA extracted; thus a concentration of the water samples was applied (centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 30 minutes). In detail, when concentrating 25 ml of sample, a total of 210 ng were obtained (concentration 6 ng/µl), while 385 ng (concentration 11 ng/µl) when concentrating 50 ml of water and 1750 ng (concentration 50 ng/µl) when concentrating 200 ml of water. Finally, 200 ml was chosen to be spiked with 75 µl of GMS for DNA extraction, providing total 1560 ng (concentration 52 ng/µl) used in the MinION sequencing experiment. In detail, the ligation genomic DNA kit (SQK-LSK109) was used, with native barcoding expansion kit (EXP-NBD114), to prepare the libraries, which were sequenced on a MK1B flowcell (FLO-MIN106 R.9.4.1) for total 21 hours and 21 minutes. A total of 6,946 reads were obtained from spiked water, for 62.7 Mb totally sequenced (Read length N50 22,825 bp). The data were analysed on ARIES (<https://w3.iss.it/site/aries/>), a webserver developed at ISS for NGS data analysis. The reads were trimmed with Porechop with default parameters and then mapped with KMA tool against a precompiled database of bacterial sequences (DTU_db1, see deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>).

Despite the low number of reads, the results showed that the sequence obtained from the pure GMS sample contained all the expected species present in the original sample with relative abundance higher than 1.5% (Table 10), even if with low mapping scores for all of them except for *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*. In the sequence obtained from the water sample spiked with GMS (Table 12), only the species present in the pure GMS sample with relative abundance higher than 6% could be retrieved and all with low mapping scores. As for the ARGs present in the GMS, they could not be retrieved in the spiked water sample (Table 14).

Despite the low sequencing coverage of sample matrices, the analysis highlighted the presence of species and ARGs not included in the GMS. In detail, two ARGs were detected, one with low and one with good mapping scores *bla*_{OXA-334} gene (template identity 81.94% and depth 0.99) and *tet*(39) (template identity 99.82% and depth 2.02). Nevertheless, it should be noted that no blank sample was sequenced. To exclude the possibility of contamination eventually arising during the manipulation of the samples or from the original kits used for sequencing, more studies would be needed including blank samples.

4. Assess feasibility/perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'complex' sample matrices

A selection of 'complex' sample matrices (i.e. either multiple bacteria present, or difficult DNA extraction, such as faeces (human and animal), milk, environmental (e.g., dust, wastewater, boot swabs) and food/feed samples) were used to evaluate the capability and practical feasibility of long-read sequencing to analyse the microbiome and resistome. 'Complex' sample matrices present several challenges such as the large microbial load as well as the presence of contaminants, which could inhibit DNA sequencing and the presence of non-bacterial DNA. Again, a known bacterial community (i.e. GMS, cfr. point 2) was spiked in to determine limits of detection and evaluate the accuracy of bacterial species and detection of the presence of ARGs.

4.1 Complex matrix: animal feces

Enterobacterales from livestock are potentially important reservoirs for antimicrobial resistance (AMR) to pass through the food chain to humans. Faecal samples were available from a recent project investigation occurrence of ARGs in Enterobacterales found on 2 cattle and 2 pig farms, in a defined geographic region in the UK (<https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000630>). These samples were collected over the course of two visits, a year apart, from four different farms, with pig samples originating from farms RH01 (RHB03 and RHB41) and RH02 (RHB02 and RHB30) and cattle samples from farms RH06 (RHB08 and RHB35) and RH10 (RHB11 and RHB 31). DNA was extracted from 8 metagenome samples (pig n=4 and cattle n=4) from the REHAB project. For long-read sequencing on ONT MinION system, DNA was isolated using GenFind v3 kit (Beckman Coulter) with the protocol modified to enable extractions from faecal samples. We also wanted to compare the effect of using lysozyme as recommended in the GenFind v3 kit and using the metapolyzyme which is a mix of six enzymes (mutanolysin, achromopeptidase, lyticase, chitinase, lysostaphin and lysozyme) that has been designed for metagenomic and meta-transcriptomic approaches⁵. In most cases there was slightly higher DNA yield obtained using the metapolyzyme (57.7ng/μl vs 61.7ng/μl). *Only RHB30 failed to extract using the metapolyzyme after several attempts and was omitted from results.

MinION sequencing was performed using the Ligation sequencing gDNA kit (SQK-LSK109) with barcodes from Native barcoding expansion kit (EXP-NBD114) and a maximum of two samples were multiplexed per flow cell (R9.4). The sequencing quality threshold was kept at default (Q=9) and high accuracy (HAC) basecalling was performed using Guppy (v6.1.5). The duration of all runs ranged between 66-70h. Sequencing and sample data summary was obtained using

⁵ Reference: <https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/deepweb/assets/sigmaaldrich/product/documents/602/346/mac4lps-mk.pdf>

NanoPlot (v1.38.0). Between 4.8 - 16.9Gb (average = 10.7Gb) of data was generated per sample. Unfortunately, RHB30-L sequence data was discarded due to poor sequencing performance. For the remaining samples, their N50s ranged from 0.64 - 2.9kb (average 1.5kb) and the number of bases ranged from 2.1×10^9 - 9.2×10^9 (average = 5.4×10^9), pre-filtering. Sequence data was processed on KMA v1.3.13 pipeline (DTU) using a custom FARMED_db database and ResFinder database for the metagenome and resistome classifications, respectively. For long-read data KMA was run using the following parameters: `-mem_mode -bc 0.7 -bcNano -ID 0.01 -ef -proxi 0.9 -na -nc -1t1 -ca`. For the short-read data the following parameters were used: `-mem_mode -ef -1t1 -apm f -nf -ID 0.01`. KMA output files (mapstat and res) were merged and filtered based on pre-defined criteria (cfr. Deliverable D-JRP12-2.1+2.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>). Further data analysis and visualisation were carried out in RStudio using relevant packages.

We first assessed the diversity of bacterial genera and resistome of cattle and pig farms and compared the effect of using either lysozyme or metapolyzyme, using the vegan (v2.6-4) package (Figure 5). For cattle farms, overall, the measured diversity metrics indicated a high microbial/AMR diversity across samples and did not appear to greatly differ between samples processed using different enzymes. For pig farms, there was a slightly higher diversity of bacterial genera for samples extracted using metapolyzyme, although this difference was less pronounced for AMR. Also, although the diversity of bacterial genera was lower in pigs than cattle, the diversity of AMR was higher in pigs. This was also observed in the study of isolates recovered from these farms which also showed that *E. coli* isolates from pig farms had a greater diversity of ARGs compared with cattle⁶.

Figure 5. Alpha diversity of bacterial genera (A) and ARGs (B).

We next compared the genera identified in either cattle or pig farms with samples collected 1 year apart (Figure 6). For cattle, the genera profiles across the 2 visits appeared different and in farms RH10 and RH06 several genera appeared in Visit 3 which were not observed a year prior in Visit 1. For example, in RH06 *Chryseobacterium* and *Lactococcus* only appeared at Visit 3. For RH10, *Chryseobacterium*, *Stenotrophomonas* were only identified at Visit 3, while

⁶ Reference: AbuOun, M., et al. (2021). A genomic epidemiological study shows that prevalence of antimicrobial resistance in Enterobacterales is associated with the livestock host, as well as antimicrobial usage. *Microbial genomics*, 7(10), 000630. <https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000630>

Lactococcus was only observed at Visit 1. In contrast, the pig farms showed a more uniform abundance of genera between farms and between Visits 1 and 3, except for RHB02 which appeared to lose the *Bacteroides* and *Psychrobacter* genera at the second visit (visit 3).

Figure 6. Heatmaps of top 20 most abundant bacterial genera. Colours within the heatmap represent log₁₀ transformed counts of reads. Samples were clustered based on hierarchy (Hierarchical clustering).

Another set of 6 animal faecal samples, collected for the national monitoring for AMR was analysed using ONT sequencing. The Purelink microbiome DNA extraction kit was used. A comparison was made between the culturing results and detected species and AMR-genes using ONT sequencing (Table 16). MRSA was cultured from 2 of the 6 samples and indeed *Staphylococcus aureus* was detected in the sequencing reads of both samples, as well as one additional sample. However, the *mecA* gene was not detected in the reads of these samples. *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* was detected in 5 samples by culture, while for only 4 of these, these species could also be detected by sequencing. ESBL-producing *E. coli* were detected in 3 of the 6 samples via culturing methods. While *E. coli* could be detected in all samples, ESBL-genes were not detected via sequencing. This dataset shows that the identification of individual species from faecal samples is feasible and further tests to determine the minimal depth to detect certain species would be a useful next step. However, the sequencing depth used here, 32,000-47,000 reads per sample, is not high enough to detect the individual AMR genes of these species which are known to have a low-level abundance in faeces.

Table 16. Comparisons of culture results and ONT sequencing

Sample	Animal	# Reads	MRSA		Campylobacter		ESBL-E. coli	
			Culture	ONT	Culture	ONT	Culture	ONT
641	Pig	39 k	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	-	<i>Escherichia</i>
644	Pig	32 k	+	<i>S. aureus</i>	+	-	-	<i>Escherichia</i>
646	Broiler	45 k	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Escherichia</i>
657	Veal	34 k	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Escherichia</i>
660	Veal	42 k	-	-	+	+	+	<i>Escherichia</i>
670	Broiler	72 k	-	<i>S. aureus</i>	+	+	+	<i>Escherichia</i>

Samples of animal faeces that were subjected to standard culture methods for EU AMR-monitoring, including selective culturing for MRSA, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Campylobacter coli* and ESBL-producing *E. coli* were compared.

In another surveillance programme for pathogen and AMR detection, pig faecal samples were sequenced, with and without the addition of the Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) bacterial mock community (see Point 2.2). The Quick-DNA HMW MagBead kit (Zymo) was used for DNA extraction, and Ligation Sequencing Kit SQK-LSK109 and Native Barcoding Expansion (PCR-free) EXP-NBD104 kits (Oxford Nanopore) were used for library preparation and sample multiplexing. The libraries were run on GridION platform (a high throughput instrument able to run up to five MinION flow cells or flongles, Oxford Nanopore Technologies). Seven Gb in 4.8 M reads were sequenced, with 3 kb N50 and 56 kb as the longest read. The output was then mapped to an in-house available manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification), and to ResFinder database for ARG predictions (Table 12 & table 15). For all spiked bacterial GMS species, reads were identified (Table 17).

Table 17. Percentage of reads matching the ID of the GMS community retrieved in GMS spiked and non-spiked pig faecal sample

Species name	% of reads matching		
	Pure GMS	non-spiked Faeces	GMS-spiked Faeces
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	44.06771	0.00602	0.5991
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	8.55369	0.3932	0.6341
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.35161	0.00539	0.1462
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	3.23897	0.01934	0.9261
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	2.60537	0.01078	0.1339
<i>Veillonella sp, oral taxon 158</i>	2.4149	0.00412	0.1617
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	1.32552	0.00095	0.0589
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	0.69483	0.00116	0.0158
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	0.31972	0.01564	0.0291
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	0.06414	0	0.0029
<i>Candida albicans</i>	0.03013	0.00011	0
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	0.02818	0	0.0004
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.01944	0.01014	0.0764
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.00292	0	0
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.00097	0.01014	0.0061
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	0.00097	0.00011	0.0005
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0	0	0.0001

While the GMS species were detected in the faecal samples (at various abundances), the remaining bacterial communities in the faecal samples, both the non-spiked and GMS-spiked faeces, were similar to each other as they were from the same pig faecal sample. This suggests that adding the GMS community does not change the original bacterial community in the complex metagenomic samples.

Finally, we also used the E.Z.N.A.[®] Stool DNA Kit (Omega Bio-tek). It allowed rapid and reliable isolation of high-quality total DNA from chicken stool samples: 5.4 µg and 3.4 µg in a total of 100 µl, for stool samples spiked with GMS and without GMS, respectively, which resulted in a mean of fragment length 10 Kb. MinION long read sequencing, using the ligation sequencing kit identified majority of the spiked species, except for species spiked at <0.01%. The DNA extraction method was used for the analysis of 'bootsocks' for onsite long read metagenomics described in WP3 (<https://zenodo.org/deposit/7433281>).

4.2 Complex matrix : human faeces

Two different clinical diarrheagenic faecal samples (A and B) both culture-negative for conventional gastrointestinal pathogens, were used and analysed as native samples or spiked with GMS (cfr. Point 2.2), in addition to being lysed by either lysozyme or bead-beating, prior to GenFind DNA extraction. Average DNA yield and total number of bp for lysozyme and bead-beating were 3051/2300 ng and 1,410,563,822/2,058,714,719, respectively. For sequencing, the samples were pooled in batches of four and prepared for sequencing on R9.4.1 flow cells using Ligation Sequencing Kit 1D (SQK-LSK109, Oxford Nanopore Technologies) and Native Barcoding Kit 1D (EXP-NBD104, Oxford Nanopore Technologies). Data was processed with a minimum quality score set to 9 and the resulting reads were demultiplexed and basecalled using Guppy (v.5.0.11). To exclude human contamination and protect patient privacy, KMA⁷ was used to map reads against the human reference genome (GRCh38) and all reads that mapped were discarded. Using KMA, the remaining reads were mapped directly against the FARMED_db and R-packages tidyverse and ggplot2 were used to analyse and visualise all results.

Generally, longer reads were observed from lysis with bead-beating. Based on species identification of GMS species in spiked clinical samples (cfr. Table 11), detection limits of both lysis procedures were approximately 0.1-1% relative abundance. The Gram-positive species *C. difficile* was only detected in pure GMS samples lysed by bead-beating (Table 10), indicating that this procedure is superior with respect to Gram-positive bacteria. However, in the spiked GMS sample (Table 12), this difference was not observed.

Clinical sample A was found to contain 61/55% relative abundance of *Klebsiella oxytoca* reads by bead-beating and lysozyme lysis, respectively (Figure 7). This opportunistic pathogen (antibiotic associated diarrhoea) is not part of the conventional diagnostics and could therefore be associated with the clinical presentation. Further analysis found significant numbers of reads related to β-lactamase resistance gene *bla_{OXY}* (ResFinder) (Figure 8) and

⁷ Clausen, P.T.L.C., Aarestrup, F.M. & Lund, O. Rapid and precise alignment of raw reads against redundant databases with KMA. BMC Bioinformatics 19, 307 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-018-2336-6>

plasmid IncFIB (PlasmidFinder) (Figure 9), both previously identified in *Klebsiella oxytoca*⁸. The clinical sample B did not contain any pathogenic species, but an abnormal high amount of *E. coli*, i.e. 60/65% relative abundance for bead-beating and lysozyme lysis, respectively (Figure 7). Reads were analysed by VirulenceFinder, but did not retrieve any *E. coli* virulence genes, so the observed imbalance of high amount of *E. coli*, may be attributed to post diarrhoea and/or prior antibiotic treatment. ResFinder analysis (Figure 8) identified resistance genes towards aminoglycosides, β -lactamases, trimethoprim, macrolide, sulphonamide, tetracycline and aminoglycoside along with reads originating from plasmids IncFIA, IncFIB, IncFII and repUS2 (Figure 9), where Inc-plasmids are well known of carrying many of the detected resistance genes found by ResFinder.

Figure 7. Relative abundance of species reads found in clinical sample A (top) and B (bottom) (grouped per gram negative and gram positive) after DNA extraction using bead-beating and lysozyme lysis.

⁸ Paskova, V. et.. al. (2018). Characterization of NDM-Encoding Plasmids From Enterobacteriaceae Recovered From Czech Hospitals. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 9, 1549. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.01549>

Figure 8. AMR gene content in clinical sample A and B (with DNA extraction using bead-beating and lysozyme lysis) and in pure GMS sample, as analysed using Resfinder with 90% identity cut-off.

Figure 9. Plasmid content in clinical sample A and B (with DNA extraction using bead-beating and lysozyme lysis) and in pure GMS sample, as analysed using PlasmidFinder with 90% identity cut-off.

4.3 Complex matrix : bootsocks

“Bootsocks” are elastic cotton tubes pulled over the boots and termed 'socks' worn underneath the shoes, plastic covering to collect faecal droppings in poultry houses. Sampling with boot swabs is a simple, safe, cost-effective and user-friendly environmental method for assessment of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* prevalence in poultry flocks. DNA was extracted by Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit (Zymo Research) from bootsocks spiked with GMS (cfr. Point 2.2), and unspiked bootsocks as a blank. Higher length DNA (50 Kb) was obtained for bootsocks, both spiked and unspiked, despite DNA recovery was lower compared to what was obtained for the pure GMS (cfr point 2.2, i.e. > 1 µg DNA /50 µl and DNA integrity (fragment length 25 Kb; DIN 8.3). DNA was sequenced by MinION using the ligation kit and Native barcoding exp 1-12 following the native barcoding genomic DNA protocol on a R9.4.1 flowcell in a single multiplex sequencing run for 72h. The critical point is the length of time to perform the high accuracy basecalling when not using GPU PC (more than 10 days). The total throughput obtained after 72h sequencing was 18.7 Gb, after filtering 17.1 Gb. The majority of them were obtained by the pure GMS (11 Gb), while only 3.3 Gb by the spiked bootsock and 2.8 Gb the blank bootsock. Discrepancies on the number of reads and the N50 reflects these unbalanced results from the different barcodes according to the input DNA. Pure GMS and spiked bootsocks were analysed through KMA using the proposed parameters. According to the KMA mapping scores, the analysis allowed detection of almost all the species reported in the list of GMS even those at lower concentration (cfr. Table 10 and 12). In Table 18 we reported the % of reads matching the ID of the GMS community retrieved in GMS pure and GMS spiked on bootsocks.

Table 18. Percentage of reads matching the ID of the GMS

Species	GMS pure		GMS spiked (bootsocks)	
	read count	%	read count	%
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	229880	7.9	85024	4.4
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	161587	5.5	18954	1.0
<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	154236	5.3	23565	1.2
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	113872	3.9	7077	0.4
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	174808	6.0	34350	1.8
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	32651	1.1	10663	0.6
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	52021	1.8	685	0.04
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	24356	0.8	11069	0.6
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	1167595	40.0	161933	8.4
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	13297	0.5	5287	0.3
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	26790	0.9	5270	0.3
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	2569	0.1	1235	0.1
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	849	0.03	815	0.04
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	29	0.001	123	0.01
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	26	0.001	197	0.01

Total read count GMS pure 2916393, GMS spiked 1921447

Other than the GMS species, we also found different common species in the bootsocks microbiota like *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, *Alcaligenes faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Bacteroides fragilis*, *Fusobacterium periodonticum*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*,

Streptococcus anginosus, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Bacteroides caccae*, *Prevotella*, *Corynebacterium*, *Campylobacter*, filtered through a minimum template length $\geq 50\text{Kb}$.

4.4 Complex matrix : food/feed samples

Insect powder and sesame paste

The food samples of ground up insect (cricket) powder and sesame paste (tahini) naturally contaminated with *Bacillus* and/or *Salmonella* were analysed using long-read sequencing. Ground cricket powder was chosen as it is a novel food in terms of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 and gaining importance as an alternative food source. The selection of contaminated tahini matrix was triggered by an ongoing international outbreak with several *Salmonella* serovars and consisted of tahini samples that were either positive or negative for *Salmonella*, while the insect powder was either *Bacillus* positive and *Salmonella* negative or *vice versa*. In all of these cases, the complex sample matrices had been analysed microbiologically and contamination levels had been determined.

DNA was extracted utilising the established Zymo Research HMW DNA Magbead Kit. In total four complex matrix samples were sequenced using ONT technology: *Salmonella*-contaminated tahini, uncontaminated tahini, *Bacillus*-positive cricket powder and *Salmonella*-positive cricket powder. The two tahini samples were multiplexed with the *Salmonella*-contaminated cricket sample and sequenced using the ONT ligation genomic sequencing (SQK-LSK109) and native barcode expansion kit (EXP-NBD104). The *Bacillus*-positive cricket sample was multiplexed separately with other isolate samples and sequenced at an earlier date using the ONT rapid kit (SQK-RBK004).

Analyses of sequencing data (Table 19) from the *Bacillus*-contaminated insect sample correctly identified the *Bacillus* contamination and further analyses were able to assemble contigs, assign a *Bacillus* clade and identify ARGs. On the other hand, the sequencing of the *Salmonella*-contaminated tahini and insect samples only yielded a small number of four or zero *Salmonella* reads, respectively. In the case of the *Salmonella*-positive tahini sample, four *Salmonella* reads were classified, but they could neither be assembled nor assigned to a certain serovar. This discrepancy between *Salmonella*- and *Bacillus*-contamination could potentially be due to the different levels of contamination, which was supposed to be very low for the *Salmonella* positive tahini sample. As had been established microbiologically, the *Bacillus* contamination in the insect sample was around 6.4×10^5 CFU/g, while the *Salmonella* contamination of the tahini sample was estimated to be much lower, since the *Enterobacteriaceae* contamination was determined to be at 2.9×10^1 CFU/ml. Nevertheless, in the sequencing results of both, the *Salmonella*-contaminated tahini sample and the negative tahini sample, the complex plant matrix, *Sesamum indicum*, was identified correctly.

Table 19. Comparison ONT and Illumina sequencing for tahini and insect food samples

	Sample							
	Tahini sample				Insect sample			
Result of microbiological testing	Contamination with <i>S. Tennessee</i> ; Enterobacteriaceae contamination at 2.9×10^1 CFU/ml		No <i>Salmonella</i> contamination		contaminated with <i>S. Wandsworth</i> and <i>S. Stanley</i> but <i>Bacillus</i> -free		<i>Salmonella</i> -free but contamination with <i>Bacillus</i> at 6.4×10^5 CFU/g	
Sequencing Technology	ONT, SQK-LSK109 3-plex	Illumina, NextSeq	ONT, SQK-LSK109 3-plex	Illumina, NextSeq	ONT, SQK-LSK109 3-plex	Illumina, NextSeq	ONT, SQK-RBK004	Illumina, NextSeq
Number of classified reads (% of total)*	89,654 (90%)	564,262 (36%)	62,406 (94%)	536,875 (31%)	244,403 (93%)	2,228,733 (64%)	2,17,658 (99%)	21,539 (12%)
Bacterial contamination identified ?	Yes, 4 <i>Salmonella</i> reads	No <i>Salmonella</i> reads	Does not apply	Does not apply	Yes, 15 <i>Salmonella</i> reads	Yes, with 131 <i>Salmonella</i> reads	Yes, nearly 50% of all classified reads identified as <i>Bacillus</i>	No, <i>Bacillus</i> reads made up 0.04% of total classified reads
Matrix identified ?	Yes (10% of classified reads)	Yes (5% of classified reads)	Yes (10% of classified reads)	Yes, (4% of classified reads)	No, but arthropods identified at 2% of total classified reads	No, but arthropods identified at 2% of total classified reads	No, but arthropods identified at 2% of total classified reads	No, but arthropods identified at 1% of total classified reads

* Classification of reads done with Kraken

These same samples were also sequenced using short-read Illumina technology (Table 19). Comparisons with the long-read sequencing data of these samples shows that the percentage of classified long-read sequencing reads far exceeded the percentage of classified short-read sequencing reads. Moreover, the complex matrix *Sesamum indicum* was more readily identified in both of the long-read sequenced tahini samples compared to short-read data and at least four *Salmonella* reads could be classified in the long-read data of the contaminated tahini sample compared to no *Salmonella* reads in corresponding short-read data. Lastly, short-read sequencing of the *Bacillus*-contaminated insect sample, could not identify *Bacillus* nor the matrix, and thus yielded no contig assembly, clade assignment or ARG identification.

Microbial fermentation products (food/feed additives, food enzymes)

Feed additives (e.g., vitamins) are often produced using genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs) to replace chemical synthesis methods, as this is more practical and requires fewer resources. The presence of a GMMs or its DNA, often harbouring ARGs used as selection marker, in microbial fermentation products is prohibited by European regulations. GMMs are currently screened for through qPCR assays targeting AMR genes and vectors, and then confirmed by targeting known specific GM constructs/events. This is done by the national reference laboratories. However, when the GMM was not previously characterised and an isolate cannot be obtained, its presence cannot be proven. A metagenomics approach is then the only way to demonstrate the presence of a GMM in a microbial fermentation product, with characterisation based on detection of AMR genes and vectors, species and unnatural associations in the GMM genome. We based the evaluation of the feasibility of this new approach on the investigation of a previously analysed sample containing a GMM *Bacillus subtilis* (rapid alert to the competent authorities (EU): RASFF 2014.1249) overproducing vitamin B2 (riboflavin), isolated and fully characterised at that time. The method was applied to a sample positive for some qPCR markers but for which no isolate could be obtained. The short- and long-read sequencing technologies were compared for their performances, including the newly released Flongle, as a smaller and cost-effective alternative. Short-read sequencing was performed with Nextera XT library preparation kit (Illumina) on an Illumina MiSeq, 2x250-bp paired-end reads with the reagent kit v3. Long-read sequencing was performed in singleplex with genomic DNA by Ligation library preparation kit (SQK-LSK109) on MinION R.9.4.1 and Flongle devices. The results were published in Buytaers et al. 2021 (Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences, Volume 2, 30 July 2021, 100023). Altogether, our method allowed to predict the presence of a GMM in the sample, based on the simultaneous detection of specific species, ARGs or vectors in species previously described as common GMM producers (Figure 10), and the encounter of unnatural associations in the genome.

This open approach can be applied to other GMM used to produce fermentation products like food enzymes. This was done in a next phase, whereby combining short- and long-read metagenomic sequencing, several *Bacillus* contaminations were detected in multiple food enzyme samples: *B. velezensis*, *B. licheniformis* and *B. amyloliquefaciens*; of which the latter two constitute unviable organisms that could not be cultivated. Furthermore, the three transgenic constructs could be fully characterised. Lastly, these contaminations were carrying a considerable load of AMR genes, representing a potential public health risk. These results have been published in D'aes et al 2022 (Life 2022, Volume 12, Issue 12, 1971).

Figure 10. Species identification in the different vitamin B2 samples

GMM14 : sample from 2014 containing a living GMM *Bacillus* strain (RASFF 2014.1249), GMMneg: sample containing DNA but negative to the previously developed qPCR methods targeting AMR markers typical of GMMs and event-specific targets of the 2014 strain, GMM16: sample from 2016 containing DNA corresponding to features of the 2014 strain, but for which no strain could be isolated). A: Kraken taxonomic classification results for Illumina ('II'), MinION ('M') and Flongle ('Flo') reads. Taxa representing <2% of the reads are counted in unclassified. B: Blast to 16S rRNA database results for MinION ('M') and Flongle ('Flo') reads. "Other" (grey): species representing <2% of the reads with hits (or for GMMneg: no hit obtained). C: Blast to nucleotide database results for MinION ('M') and Flongle ('Flo') reads. "Other" (grey): Species representing less than 2% of the reads with hits (e.g. *Streptococcus pyogenes*). Figure from Buytaers et al 2021.

Raw milk

For livestock diagnostics, detection of pathogens from mastitis suspected dairy cattle in a quick and on-site method would result in a more targeted usage of correctly prescribed antibiotics. For this purpose, raw milk samples of mastitis-suspected cows were spiked with known mastitis pathogens. Milk is considered a complex matrix as the extraction of DNA is challenging due to the high fat content. DNA was isolated using the PDQeX method (cfr. Deliverable D-JRP12-3.5; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433281>). Sequencing was performed using the Rapid sequencing kit. Samples were compared with cultures of the individual spiked organisms in pure culture (Table 19).

In all three spiked samples, the respective pathogens could be detected (Table 20) along with further parts of the microbiota that is expected in raw milk. Furthermore, part of the expected AMR genes that were present in the bacteria with which the bacteria were spiked could also be detected, along with AMR genes that were present in the milk microbiota.

While *E. coli* was detected much more readily in the milk samples than *S. uberis* and *S. aureus*, this organism was also easier to extract the DNA from in pure cultures. As such, the method may need further optimisation for determining the limit of detection. However, in all three spiked samples, the correct organism was detected using this method.

Table 20. Comparison of sequence results for pure bacterial cultures and spiked milk samples

Sample	Organism	DNA ng/ul	# mapped reads	% reads target organism
Culture 1	<i>E. coli</i>	12.5	9866	98%
Spike 1	<i>E. coli</i>	0.67	10800	96%
Culture 2	<i>S. aureus</i>	0.121	2125	98%
Spike 2	<i>S. aureus</i>	3.6	6899	3%
Culture 3	<i>S. uberis</i>	0.8	5355	98%
Spike 3	<i>S. uberis</i>	0.4	2758	33%

4.5 Complex matrix : sewage water samples

Sewage water samples are part of the surveillance programme for pathogen and AMR detection. DNA of samples, with and without the addition of the GMS bacterial mock community, was extracted using the Quick-DNA HMW MagBead kit (Zymo research). Long-read sequencing was performed using the Ligation Sequencing Kit SQK-LSK109 and Native Barcoding Expansion (PCR-free) EXP-NBD104 kits (Oxford Nanopore) for library preparation and sample multiplexing, and the GridION platform (Oxford Nanopore) for sequencing. The output was then mapped to an in-house manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification), and to ResFinder database for AMR predictions. Here we were able to detect all spiked bacterial taxa except for *C. perfringens* (Table 21). For the remaining bacterial communities (non-GMS), similar to the pig faecal samples, they were similar to each other between the two sewage metagenomes, as they originated from the same sewage sample, suggesting no major effect of adding the Zymo mock community (GMS) to complex biological samples as sewage.

Table 21. Percentage of reads matching the ID of the GMS community retrieved in GMS spiked and non-spiked sewage sample

Species name	% of reads matching		
	Pure GMS	Non-spiked sewage	GMS spiked sewage
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	44.06771	0.00564	1.17252
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	8.55369	1.71748	1.52852
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.35161	0.13668	0.35065
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	3.23897	0.04086	0.21641
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	2.60537	0.13225	0.26687
<i>Veillonella sp, oral taxon 158</i>	2.4149	0.00403	0.09368
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	1.32552	0.00141	0.05153
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	0.69483	0.25666	0.19781
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	0.31972	0.0006	0.02436
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	0.06414	0	0.00321
<i>Candida albicans</i>	0.03013	0	0.00067
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	0.02818	0	0.0004
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	0.01944	0.59444	0.5981
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.00292	0.00423	0.00482
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.00097	0.00845	0.01927
<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i> CAG:186	0.00097	0.00262	0.00683
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0	0	0

5. Assessment of added value of ONT long-read metagenomics for AMR complete gene detection and linkage to corresponding host

As demonstrated above for several matrices, ONT long-read sequencing allows for the determination of the resistome of a sample. However, it also has some additional added value for resistome determination. First, ONT long-read sequencing offers the advantage of detecting full length ARGs on a single read, in contrast to short read sequencing. This was illustrated for the GMS pure sample (singleplex) (Figure 11) and for metagenomic samples from farms (faecal samples) (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Number of reads containing a full length ARG, as detected in the pure GMS sample (singleplex)

Figure 12. AMR genes covered on a single ONT read (i.e. full length AMR gene), as detected in farm samples. Bars are coloured according to AMR class.

In addition, the advantage of long-read metagenomics is enabling our understanding of co-linkages between genes (such as AMR or virulence) and their local genetic context in host bacteria, which may include pathogenic bacteria. As a proof of concept, two approaches were used to assess the feasibility of ONT long-read metagenomics to detect such co-linkages using both pure GMS and ‘real’ samples:

1. Two-step KMA for analysis of raw long read data identifying bacterial genera and AMR genes
2. Assembled long read data classified using Kaiju or KMA, Abriicate with an AMR gene database for resistome identification.

The feasibility for linking the detected AMR genes to their host was evaluated using the GMS samples (cfr. Point 2.2). In a first approach, a 2-step KMA analysis was used. For the detected AMR genes in ‘pure’ GMS and chicken faeces ‘spiked’ GMS samples, they could be linked to their host species. In brief, this 2-step analysis consisted of extracting from the KMA output files, the reads identified as belonging to a given species during a first KMA analysis for taxonomic identification (with FARMED_db) and performing a second KMA analysis with these reads as input but using the ResFinder database. As such, if AMR genes are found on reads previously identified at the taxonomic level, the link between the two can be established (Table 22 and 23). Therefore, long-read sequencing provides potential approach for gene-host traceability in complex communities such as faeces, using KMA.

Table 22. Linking between AMR genes detection and taxonomic identification in the GMS pure sample using ONT singleplex sequencing

Species	Theoretical abundance (%)	Taxonomic identification	ARG identification						
			<i>tet(Q)</i>	<i>mdf(A)</i>	<i>tet(W)</i>	<i>cepA</i>	<i>erm(B)</i>	<i>aac(6')-laa</i>	<i>lsa(A)</i>
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14	+		+					
<i>Faecalibacteriumprausnitzii</i>	14	+/-			+				
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14	+	+			+			
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14	+			+				
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	6	+	+						
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	1.5	+					-		
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01	+/-						+	
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001	-							n/a

grey: expected AMR; n/a: not analysed because species was not detected

Taxonomic identification: +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores

; -: not detected or trace ; ARG identification: +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace.

Table 23: Linking between AMR genes detection and taxonomic identification in the GMS spiked chicken faeces sample using ONT singleplex sequencing

Species	Theoretical abundance (%)	Taxonomic identification	ARG identification							
			<i>tet(Q)</i>	<i>mdf(A)</i>	<i>tet(W)</i>	<i>cepA</i>	<i>erm(B)</i>	<i>aac(6')-laa</i>	<i>Isa(A)</i>	
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14	+		+						
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	14	+/-			+					
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14	+	+			+				
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14	+			+					
<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	6	+	+							
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	1.5	+					+			
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01	-							-	
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001	-								n/a

grey: expected AMR; ^B: also detected in unspiked matrix; n/a: not analysed because species was not detected

Taxonomic identification: +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; +/-: detection with low KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace; ARG identification: +: detection with high KMA mapping scores; -: not detected or trace.

An alternative approach was based on assembly. Longer DNA sequences increase genome coverage and length, as done for single isolate WGS, as they span larger area and loci of the bacterial genomes without the need for extensive assemblies of shorter fragments (compared to short reads). This allows for more complete genome assemblies, including their gene reservoirs (AMR or virulence genes). Assembly of the ONT sequencing reads of the GMS 'pure' sample was performed with MetaFlye⁹ v2.8.3 and detection of ARGs from the assembly with Abricate v1.0.1. With this methodology we were able to detect 5 out of the 7 resistance genes (two of them in duplicate). All of them were in contigs of large length, being some of a similar length to the reference genome of the bacteria that supposedly harbours them. From the genes detected by KMA, only *aac(6')-laa* was not detected with Abricate. Except for the contig harbouring a copy of the *tet(Q)* gene that was incorrectly classified as *Prevotella intermedia* instead of *P. corporis*, all the ARG-containing contigs were correctly assigned to the expected bacterial species by Kraken2 (v2.1.2) (Table 24). The same results were obtained in the river water sample spiked with GMS (Table 25).

Table 24. Linking of ARGs to their host using assembly in the PURE GMS sample

ARG	Contig	Contig length	Classification
<i>tet(W)</i>	contig_2	2.911.026 bp	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>
<i>tet(Q)</i>	contig_317	5.165.882 bp	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>
<i>cepA</i>	contig_317	5.165.882 bp	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>
<i>tet(Q)</i>	contig_323	421.825 bp	<i>Prevotella intermedia</i>
<i>mdf(A)</i>	contig_386	4.515 bp	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
<i>erm(B)</i>	contig_470	4.196.790 bp	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>
<i>mdf(A)</i>	contig_485	223.269 bp	<i>Escherichia coli</i>

⁹ Kolmogorov, M., et al. metaFlye: scalable long-read metagenome assembly using repeat graphs. Nat Methods 17, 1103–1110 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-020-00971-x>

Table 25. Linking of ARGs to their host using assembly in the spiked GMS river water sample

ARG	Contig	Contig length	Classification
<i>tet(W)</i>	contig_130	2.911.294 bp	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>
<i>mdf(A)</i>	contig_689	704.193 bp	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
<i>mdf(A)</i>	contig_1448	4.409 bp	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
<i>erm(B)</i>	contig_1590	4.202.341 bp	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>
<i>cep(A)</i>	contig_1752	5.166.179 bp	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>
<i>tet(Q)</i>	contig_1752	5.166.179 bp	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>
<i>tet(Q)</i>	contig_2890	423.424 bp	<i>Prevotella intermedia</i>

Long read data also allowed identification of AMR genes within metagenomic samples from farms as well as linking the AMR genes to their host species as shown in figure 13. As expected and shown for the bacterial composition work shown in WP2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258>), the assembled data resulted in identification of fewer AMR genes although some AMR co-linkages were found. These methods could be applied to the identification of other relevant genes such as heavy metal resistance and virulence genes. This method is currently labour and time intensive, but possible, however still requires full validation of the long read sequencing process as well as bioinformatics process to ensure the data truly represents the metagenomics sample. Validation was out of scope in the FARMED project.

Figure 13. Example of co-linkage of AMR to bacterial host on one cattle farm.

6. Concluding remarks and FARMED recommendations

Overall, we showed the feasibility of using long-read metagenomics to characterise the microbiome and resistome of a variety of One health sample matrices, even in matrices with challenging properties such as high fat or salt contents. Long-read MinION metagenomic sequencing offers several advantages over the already established short-read metagenomic sequencing, which includes its portability, cost of equipment as well as the longer reads containing more information, offering efficient species detection and the ability to contextualise genes of interest such as AMR and virulence genes. For the here analysed

matrices, long-read technology proved superior at identifying the selected bacterial contaminants in comparison to the short-read sequencing approach. ONT sequencing allowed the detection of the presence of full length ARG in complex samples, something which is not possible using short-read sequencing approaches.

However, there were caveats that must be considered to ensure the data generated is reliable.

- A crucial step is the DNA extraction. There are many commercially available DNA extraction kits, but researchers must consider the type of sample being used as well as different pre-processing of samples. The DNA must be in sufficient quality (long DNA fragments), purity and quantity so as not to affect the library preparation step nor to destroy the MinION flow cells downstream. The quantity of DNA to be used for long-read sequencing exceeds the one required for short-read sequencing. This might require some optimisation.
- MinION offers the ability to multiplex samples. However, if more samples are multiplexed, then this is likely to reduce the read/base yield, which in turn will result in less sequencing depth per sample and not giving a true representation of the sample matrix. In addition, a quicker, less labour-intensive ONT library preparation could be suitable for the identification of pathogens (including assembly of bacterial contigs, assignment of clades and AMR identification) rather than the exploration of all microbiomes species, but a minimum depth of MinION sequencing is required.
- It is recommended that defined control DNA, such as a microbial mock community, is added to samples to allow evaluation of the sequence data and determine the limit of detection in the specific matrix. Ideally, the defined mock community should include a range of bacteria that are not already present in the sample.

Challenges of ONT metagenomics for microbiome and resistome analysis that require further evaluation are:

- Sensitivity. As real-life samples may contain minute amount of target DNA and/or huge amount of non-target DNA, that takes up sequencing capacity in this unbiased setup, making reaching the required sensitivity challenging. Based on the obtained results here, the feasibility of using ONT sequencing for species and ARG identification in different sample matrices was demonstrated mostly for a diagnostic setting, i.e. not for the characterisation of the whole community as in microbiome studies, but when a pathogen is present in rather high concentrations. In our experiments, we could detect species in complex faecal matrix at 1.5% with a high KMA mapping score when using optimal conditions, which is a single ligation library prepared sample, per flow cell, sequenced for 72 hours.
- Confidence. We have demonstrated the feasibility of using ONT sequencing to predict the presence of certain species. However, some additional analysis, using other techniques might be necessary to increase the confidence of this finding, at the expense of the rapidity of the diagnosis. This may include employing defined control bacteria or DNA to ensure the generated MinION data is appropriate.
- Linkage of ARG to its host. This was successfully explored in FARMED in defined communities and farm microbiome, via two approaches, i.e. a 2-step KMA analysis and an assembly-based method. Although assemblers for long reads from complex metagenomics samples exist, such as Metaflye, further optimisation is needed to fully utilise the benefits of long-read sequencing in terms of linking ARGs to their respective

hosts. Alternatively, Hi-C sequencing (cfr. Deliverable D-JRP12-1.2; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433351>) or single cell metagenomics could be more suited for this linkage. This should be further investigated.

Due to the difference in the ONT technology compared to short reads sequencing, projects like FARMED are needed to fine tune its application, especially in metagenomics. As a matter of fact, the available amount of test sample can be critical when performing diagnostics or it can be difficult to obtain the right amount of DNA needed for sequencing (e.g. when extracting DNA from water). For this reason, projects aiming at testing and validating protocols for this application are essential before including the use of long-read sequencing in metagenomics in diagnostics and official testing. The FARMED project provided important inputs either on the feasibility of this application or on the protocols to be used to achieve good results. In conclusion, the FARMED project enabled nine laboratories to develop their expertise in long-read sequencing approaches and provided a valuable platform on which to further develop and improve long-read metagenomics, with the aim to make long-read metagenomics a standard method in microbiology.

7. Scientific literature

See footnotes